

Infrared Spectral Studies of Calcium-Copper Hydroxylapatites

PREMA N. PATEL and S. V. CHIRANJEEVI RAO*

Post-Graduate Department of Chemistry, G. M. College, Sambalpur

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The introduction of Cu^{2+} in calcium hydroxylapatite results in the formation of its solid solutions. In the infrared spectral studies of the samples, the vibrations corresponding to ν_4 and ν_8 are shifted to lower frequencies due to an increase in mass and binding energy as a result of substitution of Ca^{2+} by Cu^{2+} .

CALCIUM hydroxylapatite which is also called bone mineral, $\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$, (CaHA) is the major inorganic crystalline component of human skeletal system¹. It undergoes a series of cationic and anionic replacement reactions². $\text{Ca}^{2+} \rightarrow \text{Cu}^{2+}$ replacement reactions in CaHA is of extreme biological significance as it explains the mechanism of incorporation of copper into human skeletal system according to the following equation :

As a part of a series of physicochemical investigations on calcium-copper hydroxylapatites the present work is an attempt at the infrared spectral studies of these compounds.

Experimental

The details of preparation and characterisation of the samples were reported earlier³. The samples used for infrared studies were acetone washed and air dried. The infra red tracings were carried on Perkin Elmer Instrument in KBr medium.

Results and Discussion

The results of chemical analyses by the method specially worked out⁴ are given in Table I. From the analytical data, the molecular formula of each of the sample was calculated and the molar gram atomic ratio of $\frac{\text{Ca} + \text{Cu}}{\text{P}}$ of each of the sample was found to have the value 1.67 (Theoretical 1.67). The infrared traces of the samples are given in Fig. 1. The calcium

hydroxylapatite and its solid solutions with copper have hexagonal crystalline structure⁵ and are interesting examples of solid state of fairly simple molecules of tetrahedral symmetry where bands become allowed due to relaxation of the molecular symmetry⁶. Tribasic phosphate ion in the free or undistorted state is tetrahedral—a member of Td point group. In this ideal symmetry only a few absorption bands corresponding to ν_4 (570 cm^{-1}) and ν_8 (1075 cm^{-1}) of PO_4^{3-} were clearly observed. From the spectra of the samples (Fig. 1) it could be seen that the ν_8 frequency corresponding to PO_4^{3-} ion are shifted to lower frequencies and the shape of the peaks was being affected by the introduction of Cu^{2+} into the crystalline lattice. The shift of ν_8 of PO_4^{3-} vibrations to lower frequencies may be due to the effect of binding energy and atomic mass.

In Barnes' expression⁷ $\nu = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{K}{\mu}}$ which gives a

relationship between frequency, atomic mass and force constant, the vibrational frequencies are dependent on the reduced mass μ of the participating atoms and the restoring force "K" between atoms, all other terms remaining constant. When the equilibrium distance between the positive and the negative atoms of the molecule is decreased, K generally increases in the above equation. Substitution of Ca^{2+} with a nucleus like Cu^{2+} gives rise to stronger coordination of the PO_4^{3-} group to the copper ion through oxygen. This in turn weakens the P-O bond, lowering K (increasing P-O bond length) and the frequency is lowered. The PO_4^{3-} bending is normally around 520 cm^{-1} and bending modes do not shift very much under these conditions. But here the substitution is more complex, presumably because of the splitting of the triply degenerate mode at 600 cm^{-1} and thus there is an increase in the frequency from 520 cm^{-1} to 570 cm^{-1} . This theoretical explanation agrees well with the experimental data.

* For correspondence, present address : Chemist, Hinduthan Zinc Ltd., Visakhapatnam-15.

Fig. 1. Infrared Traces of Calcium-Copper Hydroxylapatites

TABLE I—CHEMICAL ANALYSES OF CALCIUM, COPPER HYDROXYLAPATITES AND THEIR SOLID SOLUTIONS

Sample No.	Wt %			Molecular Formulae	B. atom ratio Ca+Cu/P
	Ca	Cu	P		
1	39.80	—	18.61	$\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	1.68
2	27.39	16.06	17.41	$\text{Ca}_{7.5}\text{Cu}_{2.5}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	1.67
3	21.48	23.66	16.89	$\text{Ca}_{5.5}\text{Cu}_{4.5}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	1.67
4	14.76	32.30	16.30	$\text{Ca}_{4.5}\text{Cu}_{5.5}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	1.67
5	6.02	43.52	15.53	$\text{Ca}_{1.5}\text{Cu}_{8.5}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	1.67
6	—	51.25	14.76	$\text{Cu}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	1.67

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